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Understanding the Representation of Gender Biasedness in A.K. Ramanujan's "A Flowering Tree: A Woman's Tale"

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Abstract:

A.K. Ramanujan's "A Flowering Tree: A Woman's Tale" subtly explores gender biasedness in the narration and portrayal of characters. The tale portrays the woman as a protagonist with magical powers, but she remains passive and subservient to her destiny and the male characters. Despite attaining supernatural powers, she lacks agency or authority; she has been portrayed as a commodity, a woman defined by sacrifices and servility towards men. The story critiques how the role of women has been shaped in the social and familial structures, as well as the stereotypical presentation of characters, even within folklore. It also unravels how the socio-cultural patterns of a chauvinistic world influence the female characters psychologically and physically as well.

Keywords: Gender biasedness, commodification, lack of agency, stereotypical roles.

A.K. Ramanujan's "A Flowering Tree: A Woman's Tale" has been the subject of many scholarly interpretations, particularly its portrayal of gender dynamic and ecological symbolism. Many scholars have tried to study it through feminist and eco-feminist lenses. Nabanita Karanjai interprets A.K. Ramanujan's "A Flowering Tree: A Woman's Tale" as a

feminist ecological folktale that explores the metaphoric connection between womanhood and her ecology while criticizing women's passive and marginalized place in socio-cultural climes. Her readings define the cultural ramifications of the state of women in Kannada society and highlight how the tale, employing post-humanist storytelling, challenges the existing gender bias (Karanjai). Kiran Narayan also examines "A Flowering Tree: A Woman's Tale" within the broader scope of A.K. Ramanujan's writings, highlighting its thematic connections to transformation, creativity, and women's oral traditions in both South Indian and Himalayan cultural contexts (Narayan). Dr. S. Sharmila, in her paper, also explores A.K. Ramanujan's "A Flowering Tree: A Woman's Tale", analyzing the symbolic transformation of women in a flowering tree, presenting that the transformation is merely a site of commodification, a woman's sacrifice, and vulnerability in the hands of a patriarchal society (Sharmila). The present paper explores the narrative technique and character portrayal to reflect gender biases, women's position in the patriarchal society, and the often overlooked social and cultural dimensions embedded in the short story.

A.K. Ramanujan (16 March 1929 – 13 July 1993) was not only a poet, critic, and scholar but also a folklorist and translator (Ramanujan, "Flowering Tree"125). He was born to a mathematician father and was part of a Tamil Brahmin family. He took his early education from Mysore and Poona, but mainly in Belgaum and completed his doctorate in Linguistics at Indiana University, USA (Mehrotra 333-334). He spent three decades at the University of Chicago, where he got the opportunity to publish his first poetry collection and book of translations (Ramanujan, *Journeys* XXVIII). Raised in a multilingual household helped him to do the translation of many Kannada, English, and Tamil texts (Mehrotra 333-334). The year 1980 turned out to be a remarkable one in his life as he rose to fame and gained recognition, marked by new publications, experimenting with new forms, and techniques in diaries, prose, and poetry (Ramanujan, *Journeys* XXVIII). As a scholar, he also worked on various essays

reflecting Indian culture and society, concerning the structure and form of Classical Tamil and Kannada poetry. Ramanujan's legacy continues to influence Indian literature and culture, particularly through his pioneering translations and scholarly work. He is a recipient of the *MacArthur* Fellowship (Ramanujan, "Flowering Tree" 125). He passed away at the age of sixty-four in 1993, at the peak of his career (Ramanujan, *Journeys* XXV)

A Flowering Tree: A Woman's Tale is a short story by A.K. Ramanujan in his 1997 book *A Flowering Tree and Other Oral Tales* from India (Sharmila 734). It is a Kannada folklore told by women, which A. K. Ramanujan translates into English. This short story is about the life of a girl who has the power to metamorphose into a tree, set against the backdrop of gender inequality within the social structure. The story also deals with the woman's vulnerability and commodification during her transformations.

As Ethel Johnston Phelps defines, folktales are narratives about human behaviour set in a world of magic and adventure, with underlying themes of human behaviour teaching moral and social values through characters' actions (53). These stories present morals and values. Each generation reinterprets these stories to reflect the changing values and norms. In the past, folklore was a part of entertainment, but in the present times, they are used to get respite from the harsh realities of life. Traditionally, women were the primary storytellers, passing down folklore from generation to generation. The folktales serve as food for thought, conveying teachings, morals, social values, and wisdom of past generations. One thing that is quite common in these folklores is the stereotypical portrayal of sexes, where the male is supreme, the older woman is a wicked witch, and the younger woman is compliant and helpless (5–9).

In folklore, fairy tales, ballads, and oral literature, the theme remains consistent: either the gallantry and valour of men or the subjugation and plight of women. Fairy tales and folktales represent the gender stereotypes prevalent in the society of any country. The fairy and folk tales are associated with women as they are tales of old mothers and grandmothers,

positioning women within a structure of powerlessness, devoid of agency, and gender-biased subjugation. They embody the silenced and objectified nature of women in patriarchal societies. Throughout history and mythology across nations, women have always been punished for crimes they never committed, Philomela in Greek Mythology (Rossetti 13), Sita and Ahalya in *Ramayana* (Volga 25), and Sohni of Sohni Mahival and Heer of Heer Ranjha (Das 37) in Punjabi folklore. All these stories portray recurring themes of suffering, sacrifice, and honour; these innocent women endured injustice, but remained resilient and passive.

The author presents a story through a structural framework of narrative patterns. They contain techniques such as flashbacks and foreshadowing, the sequence of events, and the overall plot movement (Abrams 233–234). The structure of the narrative patterns in the short story also unveils power dynamics, where gender roles restrict women's power. Throughout the story, the author presents societal norms in which the man is the active, dominant figure while the woman is the marginalised one. A girl who acquires magical powers and marries a prince- a symbol of power- cannot assert any absolute authority. It simply illustrates how power ultimately remains in the hands of men within a household (Volga 71). Indian society considers women virtuous only when they remain passive and silent in all situations. Ultimately, the prince alone is sovereign in transforming her into a human being. This highlights that society never recognizes women as autonomous beings; men have all the authority. This supports the objectification of women in cultural, mythical, and traditional narratives as de Beauvoir asserts, "woman thus emerged as the inessential who never returned to the essential, as the absolute Other, without reciprocity" (de Beauvoir 164).

The story also emphasizes that the woman has no autonomy over her body despite possessing magical powers. Although she initially transforms herself into a flowering tree by her own choice, later, she does so at the demand of others- first her mother, then her husband, and eventually her sister-in-law. This underscores the idea that in a patriarchal world, women,

despite being powerful or attaining any supernatural power, experience a paucity of authority over their bodies and remain objectified by that patriarchal world.

This story also highlights that women are often used as objects to glorify men in myths and folk stories. Every mythology holds many stories where women are punished and used to make men heroes. As Volga asserts, women are always used as instruments by men in history to settle their scores. (Volga 4). In Indian mythology, for instance, Lord Rama waged war on Ravana to free Sita from his captivity and reclaim her. As Volga points out, even Lord Rama waged war to glorify himself; even after the war, he did not accept Sita and left her in the forest (Volga 71). This simply shows his actions were driven by a desire to glorify himself as the one to slay Ravana. The present short story similarly narrates the same idea: the girl with superpowers has no volition or agency over her powers. She possesses these powers, but that still does not make her powerful. Even the narrative, which shows the girl transforming into a tree, does not culminate in making her the powerful one; instead, it serves as an instrument to project the prince as the powerful one who resolves the problem of his wife.

The depiction of the characters in the short story also depicts gender biases. Although the main character is a woman, she remains subservient to male characters and passively awaits her fate. The narrative empowers the male characters, highlighting societal hegemony and male dominance. For instance, when the king learns about his son's interest in the flowering girl, he forcefully hands the ceremonial betel nut to her despite his mother's reluctance.

The king calmed her and softly asked her, "You have two girls at your place. Will you give us one?" The old woman's fears got worse. "How does the king know about my daughters?" she thought. She found her voice with difficulty and stammered, "All right, master. For a poor woman like me, giving a daughter is not as great a thing, is it, as your asking for one?" The king at once offered her betel leaf and betel nut (tmbla)

ceremonially on a silver platter, as a symbolic offer of betrothal. She was afraid to touch it. But the king forced it on her and sent her home. (Ramanujan, Flowering Tree 128)

This incident highlights the king using his royal coercion and the subjugation of the poor mother and the authority of the king, a male figure, reflecting the deep-rooted realities of a patriarchal society, where women are often oppressed and men hold dominant power. Ultimately, the same king delivers justice to the girl by punishing his daughter. This further reflects the idea in a patriarchal society that man is the one who brings justice. In contrast, the queen overlooked the same, reflecting that women cannot comprehend the concept of justice. The sacrifice of his daughter further portrays him as more noble, authoritative, and an administrator of justice. This depiction reinforces the traditional definition of man, who upholds moral order, even at personal cost.

Later, when the prince marries the girl, he continues to assert his dominance over her, making her vulnerable with harsh words and imposing his will upon her to transform into a flowering tree. He answered roughly, "I'll talk to you only if you do what I ask."... "I don't like all this lying and cheating. I saw you the other day becoming a beautiful tree. I saw you with my own eyes. If you don't become a tree for me, for whom will you do that?" he chided her. The bride wiped a tear from her eyes with the end of her sari and said, "Don't be angry with me. If you insist so much, I'll do as you say. Bring two pitchers of water". (Ramanujan, Flowering Tree 129)

Manifestly, the husband compels her to transform into a flowering tree, implying the dominance of her male counterpart over the woman in marriage, where her will has no place in the patriarchal world. This reflects the disregard for autonomy and women's desires and the positioning of women as a commodity to fulfil male desires.

Ultimately, the prince helps his wife become a complete human by grafting the broken twigs and branches. It reflects the idea that the husband holds authority over his wife's fate, resonating with Simone de Beauvoir's assertion that "the 'good wife' is a man's most precious treasure... she is his responsibility: he calls her his other half... through her, he displays his power to the rest of the world..." (de Beauvoir 198). Through this act, he proves that the man helps to shape the woman's destiny by guiding her towards the right path in her life in every patriarchal society. It also proves the attributes that society has inculcated, namely, that protecting and providing for a woman is the actual role of a man. Throughout a woman's life, she tries to nourish this role. This supports what Volga says, "For women, to nourish that ego and to burn themselves to ashes in it becomes the goal." (Volga 39)

Similarly, another character -the wagon driver- reinforces the same patriarchal ideology of the male as a saviour of women, much like the prince. When he sees the girl, now half-human, groaning in the gutter, he helps her out:

But the last cart driver stopped his cart and took a look. There lay a shapeless mass, a body. Only the face was a beautiful woman's face. She wasn't wearing a thing.

"Ayyo, some poor woman," he said in sorrow, and threw his turban cloth over her, and carried her to his cart, paying no heed to the dirty banter of his fellows. Soon, they came to a town. They stopped their carts there and lowered this "thing" onto a ruined pavilion. Before they drove on, the cart driver said, "Somebody may find you and feed you. You will survive." Then they drove on. (Ramanujan, Flowering Tree 131)

Every male character in this short story is shown as one who provides redemption to a woman. This dynamics reflects Simone de Beauvoir's assertion that "woman is thus the only possible salvation for each man" (de Beauvoir, 259)

The depiction of women characters in the short story reinforces traditional women's roles. The protagonist possesses magical powers, lacks authority, and has never wielded influence. She uses this mystical power to support her poor mother financially. This very unique ability eventually leads to her marriage to a prince. This reflects the idea that in a profoundly gender-biased social structure, a woman can only be a hero in a story if she possesses extraordinary or supernatural traits. Her natural qualities as a woman are seen as insufficient for heroism unless elevated by something beyond the ordinary.

Despite being entrusted with magical powers, she not only lacks autonomy but also exhibits helplessness at the hands of others. She is constantly begging and beseeching others to help her transform and retransform into the process of becoming a flowering tree. A. K. Ramanujan himself writes:

She is most vulnerable when she is a tree. She can neither speak nor move. She is most open to injury when she is most attractive, when exercising her gift of flowering. Each time she becomes a tree, she begs the one pouring the water to be careful not to hurt her. Yet, paradoxically, when she is mutilated, she cannot be healed directly. She can be made whole only by becoming the tree again, becoming vulnerable again, and trusting her husband to graft and heal her broken branches. (Ramanujan, Flowering Tree 136)

This portrayal further accentuates the notion that whenever a woman attempts to step outside her traditional roles and acts beyond the authority of a man, it leads to negative repercussions. One such incident occurs when the girl, at the insistence of her sister-in-law and friends, metamorphoses herself into a flowering tree, resulting in a limbless thing. This propels the notion that a woman should always follow her husband's directions, resulting in a disaster whenever she fails to comply with them.

The story also illustrates the idea that women deliberately withhold their agency and capabilities in order to reinforce the status of their counterparts. For instance, in the case of Sita in the *Ramayana*, she never attempts to escape from Lanka; however, she is as skilled as Rama in archery. She also refuses to go with Hanuman when he comes to rescue her because she knows that Rama intends to kill Ravana with his own hands to attain glory (Volga 71). Her decision to remain inactive and make no effort to free herself from Lanka resonates with the behaviour of the protagonist in the story, who possesses powers but still awaits her husband to help her. However, she finds a place in her sister-in-law's palace- a space and a means for self-restoration- but chooses to remain inert. This suggests the idea that women often consciously decide to suppress their strength in order to allow their counterparts to outshine them.

The daughter of the king, the main villain of the story, when she learns about the secret of the flowering girl, becomes consumed with jealousy. Her actions become detrimental to the flowering girl, resulting in her becoming a 'thing'. Another woman character, Queen, when she learns about the blunder committed by her daughter and her friends to her daughter-in-law, does nothing; instead, she couples her help to hide the secret of the daughter-in-law's disappearance. Lastly, when the flowering girl is now a 'thing', she arrives at the elder daughter's palace, and that queen does not pay any attention to her sister-in-law and never even tries to help her. Instead, when on the insistence of her house help, she permits it to be brought into the palace, but with a warning that the household chores should not be hampered. Also, she worries that bringing that thing into the palace would demand more food and care. This reflects that this queen has no worth compared to her sister-in-law, who is now not beautiful and of no worth. Neither does she empathize, nor does she try to provide her any assistance.

The presentation of these female characters in the story positions them as the agents of an antagonism and devious, proving what Simone de Beauvoir says, that "reason has no value

for them". (de Beauvoir 262). These female characters, through their indifference towards the plights of the protagonist, support the idea that women always play a role of "night, disorder, and immanence" as articulated by feminist thinkers. (de Beauvoir, 221).

To sum up, A.K. Ramanujan's "A Flowering Tree: A Woman's Tale" reflects the institutionalised gender bias in society, which continues to be mirrored in the myths, folktales, and literature of its time. Through its narrative structure and portrayal of characters, the present story's female characters are always depicted as devoid of agency and authority and reduced to commodities by the male characters. Even in stories where women are the protagonists, they still lack control over their circumstances and are rendered passive in their lives. Such narratives portray men as heroes who offer pacification, provide redemption, and ultimately resolve the plights of women.

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